

Human Transcription, Human Translation & Error-Annotated Auto-Translated Captions

Colour Key: **ASR Accuracy** ; **Terminology** ; **Accuracy** ; **Linguistic Conventions** ; **Style** ; **Locale conventions** ; **Audience appropriateness** ;

Design and markup

Human Transcription	Human Translation	YouTube Auto-Translated Captions	TikTok Auto-Translated Captions
<p>Kia lanza el nuevo programa de suscripción, Kia Flex, donde podrás alquilar tu coche desde 6 meses hasta 24 meses, ya sea eléctrico o sea de combustión. Un proceso 100% digital en donde podrás ver si se te aprueba automáticamente coger este coche o no, y podrás disponer de él en un plazo entre una o dos semanas a más tardar. ¿Incluye qué? Pues incluye todo: el mantenimiento, las averías, la asistencia en carretera. Con este</p>	<p>Kia is launching a new subscription program, Kia Flex, where you can rent your car for six to 24 months, whether it is electric or combustion. A 100% digital process where you can see whether or not you are automatically approved to collect the car, and you can have it within one to two weeks at the latest. What's included? Well, everything is included. Maintenance, breakdowns, roadside assistance. With this program, we're running out of excuses not to</p>	<p>Kia launches (unidiomatic style; MINOR) the (grammar; NEUTRAL) new Kia Flex (grammar; NEUTRAL) subscription program (punctuation; MINOR) where you can rent your car from (grammar; NEUTRAL) 6 (inconsistent with external reference; NEUTRAL) months (awkward style; NEUTRAL) to 24 months, whether it is electric or combustion. (punctuation; MINOR) a (capitalisation; MINOR) 100% digital process where you can see if (grammar; NEUTRAL) you are automatically approved to take (grammar; NEUTRAL) this (grammar; MINOR) car. (punctuation; MINOR) or not (grammar; NEUTRAL) and you can have it within a period of (unidiomatic</p>	<p>Guía (substitution; MAJOR) launches (unidiomatic style; MINOR) (grammar; MINOR) new subscription program Flex guide (substitution; MAJOR), where you can rent your car from (grammar; NEUTRAL) 6 (inconsistent with external reference; NEUTRAL) months (awkward style; NEUTRAL) to 24 months, either (grammar; MINOR) electric or combustion. I (substitution; MINOR) 100x100 (substitution; MINOR) digital process where you can see if (grammar; NEUTRAL) you are automatically approved to take (grammar; NEUTRAL) this (grammar; MINOR) car or not (grammar; NEUTRAL) (punctuation; MINOR) and you will be able to dispose of it</p>

<p>programa se nos van acabando las excusas para no disponer de un vehículo Kia y de estos nuevos servicios de movilidad. Kia, movement that inspires.</p>	<p>have a Kia vehicle and these new mobility services. Kia, movement that inspires.</p>	<p>style; MINOR one or two weeks at the latest, (punctuation; MINOR) including (substitution; MINOR) what (punctuation; MINOR) (deletion; MINOR) is included, (punctuation; MINOR) all (substitution; MINOR) (punctuation; MINOR) maintenance (capitalisation; MINOR), breakdowns, roadside assistance (textual conventions; MINOR). With this program (punctuation; NEUTRAL) we are (language register; NEUTRAL) running out of (deletion; MINOR) opportunities (addition; MINOR) to not (grammar; MINOR) have a Kia vehicle and these new mobility services. [Music] (insertion; NEUTRAL) (deletion; MINOR)</p>	<p>(mistranslation; MINOR) within 1 (substitution; MINOR) period of time (unidiomatic style; MINOR) (grammar; MINOR) 1 (substitution; NEUTRAL) to 2 (substitution; NEUTRAL) weeks at the latest. Including (substitution; MINOR) what? Well, including (substitution; MINOR) all (punctuation; MINOR) maintenance (capitalisation; MINOR), breakdowns, roadside assistance (textual conventions; MINOR). With this program (punctuation; NEUTRAL) we are (language register; NEUTRAL) running out of excuses in order to not have (mistranslation; MINOR) 1 (substitution; MINOR) vehicle Kia (grammar; MINOR) and these new Kia (addition; NEUTRAL) mobility services (punctuation; MINOR) (deletion; MINOR)</p>
<p>Tenemos aquí nuestro nuevo EV3 que, en línea con nuestros eléctricos, lleva los 10 materiales</p>	<p>Here we have our new EV3, which, in line with our electric vehicles, has Kia's 10 essential</p>	<p>[Music] (insertion; NEUTRAL) Here we have our new iv3 (substitution; MAJOR), which (punctuation; MINOR) in line with our electrics</p>	<p>We have here (grammar; NEUTRAL) our new ibi 3 (substitution; MAJOR) which, in line with our electrics (textual conventions; NEUTRAL),</p>

<p>imprescindibles de Kia, en nuestra apuesta por ser más sostenibles y cuidar también del medio ambiente. Tienen una tapicería bitono hecha de cuero vegano. También llevan elementos reciclados del PET, que es el plástico más reciclable del mundo. Este material está también en el revestimiento del techo, en las puertas, en consonancia con los 10 materiales imprescindibles de Kia. Los asientos son muy cómodos. Los puedes ajustar para que estén como mejor te venga a ti. También tienes dos posiciones de memoria por si tienes que intercambiar el coche con alguien más, y la opción de tener los</p>	<p>materials, in our commitment to be more sustainable and take care of the environment. They have a two-tone upholstery made of vegan leather. They also contain elements of recycled PET, which is the most recyclable plastic in the world. This material is also found in the headliner and door panelling, in-keeping with Kia's 10 essential materials. The seats are very comfortable. You can adjust them to best suit you. You also have two memory positions, in case you have to switch cars with someone else, and the option of having both heated and ventilated seats to adapt to any weather situation. Kia, movement that inspires.</p>	<p>(textual conventions; NEUTRAL) (punctuation; MINOR) has the 10 essential materials from Kia (unidiomatic style; MINOR) (punctuation; NEUTRAL) in our commitment to be more sustainable and also (awkward style; NEUTRAL) take care of the environment. They have a two-tone upholstery made of vegan leather. They also have (unidiomatic style; MINOR) recycled elements of PET, which is the most recyclable plastic in the world. This material is also in the headliner and the doors (mistranslation; MINOR) (punctuation; NEUTRAL) in line (grammar; NEUTRAL) with Kia's 10 essential materials. The seats are very comfortable. You can adjust them to suit you best (grammar; NEUTRAL). You also have two memory positions (punctuation; NEUTRAL) in case you have to exchange the car (language register; MINOR) with someone else (punctuation; NEUTRAL) and the option of having both heated and ventilated seats to adapt to any weather situation. (Music)</p>	<p>carries (unidiomatic style; MINOR) Kia's 10 recycled (mistranslation; MINOR) materials (punctuation; NEUTRAL) in our commitment to be more sustainable and to take care of also of (grammar; NEUTRAL) the 2nd (insertion; MINOR) environment. They have 1 (substitution; MINOR) bitono (untranslated; MAJOR) upholstery made of vegan leather (punctuation; MINOR) (omission; MINOR) also carry (unidiomatic style; MINOR) elements characteristic of the pet (mistranslation; MAJOR), which is the most (omission; MAJOR) plastic in the world. This material is also in the roof covering (wrong term; MAJOR) (punctuation; MINOR) at (grammar; MINOR) the doors (mistranslation; MINOR) in harmony (grammar; NEUTRAL) with Kia's 10 recycled (mistranslation; MINOR) materials (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) the seats are very comfortable (punctuation; MINOR) you (capitalisation; MINOR) can adjust them to be as best</p>
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<p>asientos tanto calefactados como ventilados para adaptarse a cualquier situación climática. Kia, movement that inspires.</p>		<p>(insertion; NEUTRAL) (deletion; MINOR)</p>	<p>suits you (textual conventions; MINOR). You also have 2 (inconsistent with external reference; NEUTRAL) memory positions in case you have to swap cars with someone else (punctuation; NEUTRAL) and the option of having both heated seats as ventilated (textual conventions; MINOR) to adapt to any climatic situation (mistranslation; MINOR) (punctuation; MINOR) (deletion; MINOR)</p>
<p>El maletero de EV3 es uno de los más grandes de su segmento con 460 l de capacidad. Aparte de eso, tiene un doble fondo, por lo que podemos tener la bandeja arriba y usar el compartimento de abajo para guardar los cables de carga, y si necesitas más espacio, lo bajas y tienes todo este espacio extra disponible. No solo</p>	<p>The EV3's trunk is one of the largest in its segment with a capacity of 460 litres. Apart from that, it has a double bottom, so we can keep the tray up and use the compartment below to store charging cables, and if you need more space, you lower it and you have all this extra space available. It's not just the trunk, but also</p>	<p>[Music] (insertion; NEUTRAL) the (capitalisation; MINOR) trunk of the elb 3 (substitution; MAJOR) is one of the largest in its segment with 460 l (inconsistent with external reference; NEUTRAL) of capacity (awkward style; NEUTRAL) (punctuation; MINOR)(capitalisation; MINOR) apart from that (punctuation; NEUTRAL) it has a double bottom (punctuation; NEUTRAL) so we can have (grammar; NEUTRAL) the tray up and use the compartment below to store the (grammar; NEUTRAL)</p>	<p>The trunk of the IBI 3 (substitution; MAJOR) is 1 (substitution; MINOR) of the largest in its segment with 460l (inconsistent with external reference; NEUTRAL) of capacity (awkward style; NEUTRAL) (punctuation; MINOR) Apart from that (punctuation; NEUTRAL) it has 1 (substitution; MINOR) double bottom (punctuation; NEUTRAL) so we can have (grammar; NEUTRAL) the tray above (grammar; MINOR) and use the compartment below to store the (grammar; NEUTRAL) charging</p>

<p>es el maletero, sino también el espacio interior. Los asientos traseros permiten viajar a tres ocupantes con la máxima comodidad, y el espacio delantero, con su bandeja deslizante, ofrece un confort extra a los conductores. Y por último mencionar, este coche también tiene un Frunk o maletero delantero de hasta 25 l de capacidad para albergar, por ejemplo, un cable de carga. Kia, movement that inspires.</p>	<p>the interior. The rear seats allow three occupants to travel with maximum comfort, and the front space, with its sliding tray, offers extra comfort to drivers. And finally, this car also has a Frunk, or front trunk, with up to 25 litres of capacity to hold, for example, a charging cable. Kia, movement that inspires.</p>	<p>charging cables (punctuation; MINOR) and if you need more Music (insertion; MINOR) space (punctuation; NEUTRAL) you lower it and you have all this extra space available (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) it is (language register; NEUTRAL) not only the trunk (awkward style; MINOR) but also the interior space (grammar; NEUTRAL) (punctuation; MINOR)(capitalisation; MINOR) the rear seats allow three occupants to travel with maximum comfort (punctuation; NEUTRAL) and the front space (punctuation; MINOR) with its sliding tray (punctuation; MINOR) offers extra comfort to drivers (punctuation; MINOR) And finally mention (textual conventions; MINOR) (punctuation; NEUTRAL) this car also has a Frank (substitution; MINOR) (punctuation; NEUTRAL) or front trunk (punctuation; NEUTRAL) of (grammar; NEUTRAL) up to 25 l (inconsistent with external reference;</p>	<p>cables (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) AND if you need more space (punctuation; NEUTRAL) you bring it down (awkward style; NEUTRAL) and you have all this extra space available. It is (language register; NEUTRAL) not only the trunk (awkward style; MINOR) (punctuation; NEUTRAL) but also the interior space (punctuation; MINOR) The rear seats allow 3 (substitution; NEUTRAL) occupants to travel with maximum comfort (punctuation; NEUTRAL) and the front space (punctuation; MINOR) with its sliding tray (punctuation; MINOR) offers 1 (substitution; MINOR) extra comfort to drivers. And lastly mention (textual conventions; MINOR) (punctuation; NEUTRAL) this car also has 1 (substitution; MINOR) Frank (substitution; MINOR) or front trunk (punctuation; NEUTRAL) (grammar; MINOR) up to 25 l (inconsistent with external reference; NEUTRAL) capacity to accommodate (awkward style; NEUTRAL)</p>
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		<p>NEUTRAL) (grammar; MINOR) capacity to house (awkward style; NEUTRAL) (punctuation; NEUTRAL) for example (punctuation; NEUTRAL) a charging cable (punctuation; MINOR) [Music] (insertion; NEUTRAL)(deletion; MINOR)</p>	<p>(punctuation; NEUTRAL) for example (punctuation; NEUTRAL) I (substitution; MINOR) charging cable. (deletion; MINOR)</p>
<p>¿Cómo afecta tu conducción a la autonomía del vehículo eléctrico? Al igual que sucede con los vehículos de combustión, si tienes una conducción enérgica, descenderá. Por el contrario, conduces de forma eficiente, la autonomía aumentará. Para tener información más detallada, podrás recurrir a la pantalla central. En ella podrás ver la autonomía total, en este caso 377 km. Hemos recorrido 782 km y</p>	<p>How does your driving affect an electric vehicle's range? Just like with combustion vehicles, if your driving is energetic, it will decrease. Conversely, if you drive efficiently, the range will increase. For more detailed information, you can refer to the centre display. There, you can see the total range, in this case 377 km. We have traveled 782 km and have an average consumption of 16.9 kW</p>	<p>How your driving affects the autonomy (wrong term; MAJOR) of the electric vehicle (grammar; MINOR) (punctuation; MINOR) as it happens (unidiomatic style; NEUTRAL) with combustion vehicles (punctuation; MINOR) if you have an energetic drive (textual conventions; MINOR) it will decrease. (punctuation; NEUTRAL) on the contrary (punctuation; MINOR) if you drive efficiently (punctuation; NEUTRAL) the autonomy (wrong term; MAJOR) will increase (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) for more detailed information (punctuation; NEUTRAL) you can use (grammar; MINOR) the central screen</p>	<p>How does your driving affect to (grammar; MINOR) the autonomy (wrong term; MAJOR) of the electric vehicle? As (grammar; NEUTRAL) with combustion vehicles, if you have I (substitution; MINOR) energetic conduction (mistranslation; MINOR) it will descend (grammar; MINOR). On the contrary (awkward style; NEUTRAL), drives efficiently (grammar; MINOR), autonomy (wrong term; MAJOR) will increase. For more detailed information (punctuation; NEUTRAL) you will be able to (awkward style; NEUTRAL) use (grammar; MINOR) the central screen (inconsistent with terminology resource; MINOR). In</p>

<p>tenemos un consumo medio de 16,9 kW a los 100 km. Por último, en el espacio central inferior, podremos ver la barra de consumo instantáneo. En ella nos mostrará, de forma muy gráfica, el consumo que realizamos tanto por pisar el acelerador más o menos, si llevamos climatizador, si estamos subiendo una montaña, para tenernos una idea súper clara de cuánto estamos consumiendo. El sistema de infotainment de Kia te permitirá reflejar los datos del consumo desde el punto que tú determines, al iniciar el viaje, desde la última recarga, o desde que te compraste el vehículo. Kia, movement that inspires.</p>	<p>per 100 km. Finally, in the lower central space, we can see the instant consumption bar. It will show us, in great detail, the consumption we make by stepping on the accelerator more or less, if we have the air conditioning on, if we are going up a mountain, giving us a super clear idea of how much we are consuming. Kia's infotainment system will allow you to display consumption data from the point you determine, from the start of the trip, since the last recharge, or since you bought the vehicle. Kia, movement that inspires.</p>	<p>(inconsistent with terminology resource; MINOR) (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) in it (grammar; MINOR) (punctuation; NEUTRAL) you will be able to (awkward style; NEUTRAL) see the total autonomy (wrong term; MAJOR) (punctuation; MINOR) in this case (punctuation; NEUTRAL) 377 km (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) we have traveled 782 km (capitalisation; MINOR) And we have an average consumption of 16.9 kw (inconsistent with external reference; NEUTRAL) at 100 kw (mistranslation; MINOR) (punctuation; MINOR)(capitalisation; MINOR) finally in the lower central space (punctuation; NEUTRAL) we will be able to (awkward style; NEUTRAL) see the instantaneous consumption bar (inconsistent with terminology resource; MINOR) (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) in (grammar; MINOR) it will show us (punctuation; NEUTRAL) in a very graphic way (unidiomatic style;</p>	<p>Ella (substitution; MINOR) you will be able to see the total autonomy (wrong term; MAJOR), in this case 377km. We have covered 782km and we have 1 (substitution; MINOR) 2nd (substitution; MINOR) consumption of 16.9kW after (grammar; MINOR) 100km. Finally, in the lower central space (punctuation; NEUTRAL) I need to (mistranslation; MINOR) see the instant consumption bar. In Ella (substitution; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) it will show us (punctuation; NEUTRAL) in a very graphic way (unidiomatic style; MINOR) . (punctuation; MINOR) the consumption we make, (punctuation; MINOR) so much for (mistranslation; MINOR) stepping on the accelerator, (punctuation; MINOR) more or less (punctuation; MINOR) if we carry (grammar; MINOR) air conditioning. (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) If we are climbing 1 (substitution; MINOR) mountain. (punctuation; MINOR) To have (grammar; MINOR) I</p>
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		<p>MINOR) (punctuation; MINOR) the consumption that (grammar; NEUTRAL) we make by both pressing (grammar; NEUTRAL) the accelerator more or less (textual conventions; MINOR) (punctuation; MINOR) if we have air conditioning (grammar; MINOR) (punctuation; MINOR) if we are going up a mountain (punctuation; MINOR) it will give (grammar; MINOR) us a super clear idea of how much we are consuming (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) the Kia infotainment system (awkward style; NEUTRAL) will allow you to reflect (grammar; MINOR) the (grammar; MINOR) consumption data from the point that (grammar; NEUTRAL) you determine (capitalisation; MINOR) When starting the trip (grammar; MINOR) (punctuation; MINOR) since the last recharge (punctuation; MINOR) or since you bought the vehicle (punctuation; MINOR) [Music] (insertion; NEUTRAL) (deletion; MINOR)</p>	<p>(substitution; MINOR) Idea super clear (substitution; MINOR) about how much we are consuming, Kia's boot (substitution; MAJOR) system will allow you to reflect (grammar; MINOR) consumption data from the point you determine (punctuation; MINOR) at (grammar; MINOR) the start of the trip, since the last recharge (punctuation; MINOR) or since you bought the vehicle (punctuation; MINOR) Kia (deletion; MINOR)</p>
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<p>Hoy vamos a ver cómo cargar tu vehículo eléctrico o híbrido enchufable. En este caso, estamos con un NIRO. Tiene la portada en la frontal. Hay otros vehículos que la pueden tener en el lateral frontal izquierdo o en el lateral trasero derecho. Con el coche abierto, tendremos que abrir el portal frontal. Vamos a encontrar tanto la carga lenta como rápida. La lenta se tratará solo de uno de los orificios y la carga rápida, los dos orificios. Tendréis que acudir a algún cargador. Habrá cargadores gratuitos, los cuales directamente conectaréis vuestro cargador y la carga se iniciará, o habrá cargadores de pago, los cuales tendréis que</p>	<p>Today we're going to see how to charge your electric or plug-in hybrid vehicle. In this case, we're with a NIRO. It has the cover on the front. There are other vehicles that have it on the front-left side or on the rear-right side. With the car opened, we will have to open the front cover. We're going to see both the slow and fast charge. Slow will be only one of the ports and fast, both ports. You will have to access a charger. There will be free chargers, where you will directly connect your charger and the charging will start, or paid chargers, where you will have to use the platform or card that the charger requires. You must take it, insert it, and close the</p>	<p>(capitalisation; MINOR) today (language register; NEUTRAL) we are going to see how to charge your electric or plug-in hybrid vehicle (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) in this case (punctuation; NEUTRAL) we are (language register; NEUTRAL) with an (grammar; MINOR) eniro (substitution; MAJOR) (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) it has the cover on the front (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) there are other vehicles that (grammar; MINOR) can have it on the front left (spelling; NEUTRAL) side or on the rear (omission; MINOR) side (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) in the open car (grammar; MINOR) (punctuation; MINOR) we will have to open the front (wrong term; MINOR) (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) we will find (awkward style; NEUTRAL) both the slow and fast charge (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR)</p>	<p>Today (grammar; NEUTRAL) we will see (grammar; NEUTRAL) how to charge your electric vehicle or (wrong term; MAJOR) plug-in connector. In this case (punctuation; NEUTRAL) we are (language register; NEUTRAL) with (substitution; MINOR) 1 (substitution; MAJOR) eniro. It has the front cover (undertranslation; MINOR), (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) there are other vehicles that (grammar; NEUTRAL) can (grammar; NEUTRAL) have it on the side left front (grammar; MINOR) or on the right left side (mistranslation; MINOR). With the car (grammar; MINOR) open (grammar; MINOR), we will have to open the front (wrong term; MINOR) portal (grammar; MINOR). Let's find (grammar; MINOR) both (grammar; NEUTRAL) slow and fast (grammar; MINOR) charging (grammar; MINOR). The slow one (awkward style; MINOR) will deal with (unidiomatic style; MINOR) only (substitution; MINOR) 1 (wrong term; MINOR) of the holes (wrong term; MINOR) and fast charging (awkward style; MINOR), the (substitution; NEUTRAL) 2 (wrong term; MINOR) holes</p>
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<p>utilizar la plataforma o tarjeta que requiera el cargador. Deberéis cogerla, introducirla y cerrar el vehículo. Escucharéis un pequeño clac que os confirmará que se ha iniciado la carga. Podréis ver en las luces frontales que la carga se inicia, como veréis que suben poquito a poco, e igualmente en la pantalla de infotainment interior. Kia, movement that inspires.</p>	<p>vehicle. You will hear a little click which will confirm that charging has started. You will be able to see from the front lights that the charge is starting, as you will see that they go up little by little, and also in the interior infotainment screen. Kia, movement that inspires.</p>	<p>the slow one (awkward style; MINOR) will only be one of the holes (wrong term; MINOR) and the fast charge (awkward style; MINOR) (punctuation; MINOR) both holes (wrong term; MINOR) (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) you will have to go to (grammar; NEUTRAL) a charger (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) there will be free chargers (punctuation; MINOR) to which I will directly connect (substitution; MINOR) your charger and the charge (unidiomatic style; MINOR) will start (punctuation; MINOR) or there will be (awkward style; NEUTRAL) paid chargers (punctuation; NEUTRAL) which you will have (textual conventions; MINOR) to use the platform or card that the charger requires (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) you must take it (punctuation; MINOR) insert it (punctuation; NEUTRAL) and close the vehicle (punctuation; MINOR) I will hear (substitution; MINOR) a small clac (substitution;</p>	<p>(wrong term; MINOR). You will have to go to (grammar; NEUTRAL) a charger. There will be free chargers, which directly you will connect your charger (grammar; MINOR) and the load (wrong term; MINOR) will start, or there will be payment chargers (awkward style; MINOR), which (grammar; NEUTRAL) you will have to use the platform or card required by the charger (grammar; NEUTRAL). You must take it, introduce (grammar; MINOR) it (punctuation; NEUTRAL) and close the vehicle. You will hear I (substitution; MINOR) little Black (substitution; CRITICAL) which will confirm that the load (wrong term; MINOR) has started. You will be able to see on the headlights (mistranslation; MAJOR) that the load (wrong term; MINOR) is initiated (grammar; MINOR), as you will see that they are gradually increasing (textual conventions; MINOR) and also on the interior infraexperiment (substitution; MAJOR) screen (punctuation; MINOR) (deletion; MINOR)</p>
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		<p>MINOR that (grammar; NEUTRAL) will confirm that the charge (grammar; NEUTRAL) has started (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) you will be able to see in the front lights that the charge starts (unidiomatic style; MINOR) (punctuation; NEUTRAL) as you will see that they go up little by little (punctuation; NEUTRAL) and also on the interior infotainment screen (punctuation; MINOR) [Music] (insertion; NEUTRAL) (deletion; MINOR)</p>	
<p>¡Hola, hola! En este How To te vamos a explicar qué hacer si el mando solar de tu televisor no responde. ¡Comenzamos! Lo primero que tenemos que hacer es verificar si el mando está cargado y conectado por Bluetooth al televisor. ¿Cómo? Sitúate cerca del televisor y pulsa</p>	<p>Hello, hello! In this How To, we are going to explain what to do if your TV's solar remote isn't responding. Let's get started! The first thing we need to do is to check if the controller is charged and connected to the TV via Bluetooth. How? Stand close to the TV and press the Return</p>	<p>Hello (punctuation; MINOR) hello (punctuation; MINOR) in (capitalisation; MINOR) this howu (substitution; MINOR) (punctuation; NEUTRAL) we are going to explain what to do if the solar remote control of your TV (awkward style; MINOR) does not respond (grammar; MINOR). We begin by first having to (grammar; MINOR) check if the remote control is charged and connected by Bluetooth to the TV</p>	<p>Hello (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) Hello (punctuation; MINOR) In this house tour (substitution; MINOR) we are going to explain what to do if your TV's solar controller (undertranslation; NEUTRAL) doesn't respond (grammar; MINOR) (punctuation; MINOR) Let's start (grammar; NEUTRAL) (punctuation; MINOR) The first thing we need to do is to check if the</p>

<p>simultáneamente los botones Return Play/Pause unos segundos. El televisor debería emparejarse con el mando y mostrar el estado de carga de la batería. De lo contrario, si no se empareja o está descargado, recuerda que puedes cargarlo con luz interior o exterior, con un cargador USB tipo C, como el de tu teléfono móvil, o absorbiendo ondas RF, como las del router, que las transforma en energía y lo carga. Espero que esta info te haya sacado de apuros. ¡Nos vemos en un próximo How To!</p>	<p>and Play/Pause buttons simultaneously for a few seconds. The TV should pair with the remote control and display the battery charge status. On the other hand, if it doesn't pair or if it's dead, remember that you can charge it with indoor or outdoor light, with a USB type C charger, like that of your mobile phone, or by absorbing RF waves, like those from your router, which transform into power and charge it. I hope this info has helped you out, see you in the next How To!</p>	<p>(grammar; MINOR), (punctuation; MINOR) (substitution; MINOR) such as (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) standing near (grammar; MINOR) the TV and simultaneously (grammar; NEUTRAL) pressing the return (capitalisation; MINOR) (grammar; MINOR) Play (substitution; MINOR) buttons for a few seconds (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) the TV should pair with the remote control and show (grammar; NEUTRAL) the battery charge status, (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) otherwise (grammar; NEUTRAL) if it does not (language register; NEUTRAL) pair or is discharged (mistranslation; MINOR). (punctuation; MINOR) Remember (capitalisation; MINOR) that you can charge it with indoor or outdoor light (punctuation; MINOR) with a USB type C charger (punctuation; MINOR) like the one on (grammar; MINOR) your mobile phone (punctuation; MINOR) or by</p>	<p>controller is charged and connected via Bluetooth to the TV (grammar; MINOR) (punctuation; MINOR) How (punctuation; MINOR) to Stay near the TV (grammar; MINOR) and simultaneously press the (capitalisation; MINOR) return buttons Play pause A few seconds (grammar; MINOR) (punctuation; MINOR) The TV should match (mistranslation; MINOR) the controller (undertranslation; NEUTRAL) and show (grammar; NEUTRAL) the battery charge status, (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) otherwise (grammar; NEUTRAL) if it does not (language register; NEUTRAL) match (mistranslation; MINOR) or is downloaded (mistranslation; MINOR). (punctuation; MINOR) Remember that you can charge it with indoor or outdoor light (punctuation; MINOR) with I (substitution; MINOR) USB type c (capitalisation; MINOR) charger (punctuation; NEUTRAL) like the one on (grammar; MINOR) your cell</p>
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		<p>absorbing RF waves (punctuation; MINOR) like those of the (grammar; MINOR) router (punctuation; MINOR) that (grammar; MINOR) transforms them into energy (mistranslation; MINOR) (grammar; MINOR) and charges it (grammar; MINOR). I hope this info has gotten you out of trouble (awkward phrasing; NEUTRAL) (punctuation; NEUTRAL) See (capitalisation; NEUTRAL) you in a next howu (substitution; MINOR) (punctuation; MINOR)</p>	<p>(unidiomatic style; MINOR) phone, or by absorbing RF waves (punctuation; NEUTRAL) like those of the router (grammar; MINOR) (punctuation; MINOR) hat (grammar; MINOR) transforms them into energy (mistranslation; MINOR) (grammar; MINOR) and charges it (grammar; MINOR) I hope this info has gotten you out of trouble. (awkward phrasing; NEUTRAL) See (capitalisation; NEUTRAL) you in I (substitution; MINOR) next house tour.(substitution; MINOR)</p>
<p>Hola, ¡Hola! Hoy voy a enseñarte cómo actualizar el software de tu televisor con un USB desde la página web de Samsung. Lo primero que tendrás que hacer es seleccionar el menú. Marcarás Configuración, Asistencia y marcamos Acerca de este televisor. Verifica el código de tu</p>	<p>Hello, hello! Today I'm going to show you how to update your TV's software with a USB from the Samsung website. The first thing you'll have to do is select the menu. You'll select Settings, Support and About this TV. Verify your TV's code and the software version.</p>	<p>Hello (punctuation; MINOR) hello (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) today I am going to teach (language register; MINOR) you (capitalisation; MINOR) How to update the software on your TV (language register; NEUTRAL) with a USB from the Samsung website (punctuation; MINOR) The first thing you will (language register; NEUTRAL) have to do is select the menu. (punctuation;</p>	<p>Hello, hello! Today I'm going to show you how to update your TV software with I (substitution; MINOR) USB from Samsung's website (grammar; NEUTRAL). The first thing you will (language register; NEUTRAL) have to do is to grammar; MINOR) select the menu. punctuation; MINOR)(capitalisation; MINOR) you will (language register; NEUTRAL) mark (mistranslation; MINOR) configuration</p>

<p>televisor y la versión del software. Acuérdate de estos datos ya que van a ser muy importantes cuando vayas a la página web de Samsung y descargues la última versión del software de tu televisor.</p> <p>Descomprime el archivo y guárdala en la carpeta de nivel superior de la unidad USB conectada a tu PC. Sigue estos pasos porque de lo contrario el televisor no podrá localizar el paquete de actualización. Inserte la unidad USB externa en la ranura diseñada para estos dispositivos del televisor. Una vez realizados estos pasos, deberás ir a Configuración, admitir Actualización de software, y Actualizar ahora. ¡Importante! No</p>	<p>Remember these details as they will be very important when you go to the Samsung website and download the latest version of your TV's software. Unzip the file and save it in the top folder of the USB drive connected to your PC. Follow these steps, because otherwise the TV will not be able to locate the update package.</p> <p>Insert the external USB drive into the designated slot for these devices on the TV. Once you have completed these steps, you will need to go to Settings, allow Software Update, and Update Now. Important! Do not turn off the TV or remove the USB drive until the update is</p>	<p>MINOR)(capitalisation; MINOR) (grammar; MINOR) select (capitalisation; MINOR) settings, (capitalisation; MINOR) support and select (awkward style; NEUTRAL) (capitalisation; MINOR) about this TV. (punctuation; MINOR)(capitalisation; MINOR) check (mistranslation; MINOR) the code of your TV and the software version. Remember these details as they will be very important (capitalisation; MINOR) When you go to the Samsung website and download the latest version of your TV's software. (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) unzip the file and save it in the top-level (unidiomatic style; MINOR) folder of the USB drive connected to your PC. (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) follow these steps (punctuation; NEUTRAL) because otherwise the TV will not be able to locate the update package (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) insert the external USB drive into the slot</p>	<p>(capitalisation; MINOR)(inconsistent with terminology resource; MINOR), assistance (inconsistent with terminology resource; MINOR) punctuation; MINOR)(capitalisation; MINOR) and we mark (mistranslation; MINOR) about this TV (capitalisation; MINOR). Verify your TV (grammar; NEUTRAL) code and (grammar; NEUTRAL) software version. Remember this information (grammar; NEUTRAL) as they are going (language register; NEUTRAL) to be very important. (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) When you go to Samsung's website (language register; NEUTRAL) and download the latest software version from your TV (grammar; MINOR), (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) decompresses (mistranslation; MINOR) the file and save it in the top level unidiomatic style; MINOR) folder of the unit USB (inconsistent with terminology resource; MINOR)</p>
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<p>apagues el televisor ni extraigas la unidad USB hasta que la actualización haya finalizado. ¡Listo!</p>	<p>complete. Ready!</p>	<p>designed (grammar; NEUTRAL) for these devices on the TV. Once you have completed these steps (punctuation; NEUTRAL) you will have to go to settings (capitalisation; MINOR), support (inconsistent with terminology resource; MINOR) software update (capitalisation; MINOR) (punctuation; NEUTRAL) and update (capitalisation; MINOR) now, (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) important (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) do not turn off the TV or remove the USB drive until the update is complete. (capitalisation; MINOR) ready (punctuation; MINOR)</p>	<p>connected to your PC. Follow these steps (punctuation; NEUTRAL) because otherwise the TV will not be able to locate the upgrade (inconsistent with terminology resource; NEUTRAL) package. Insert the external USB drive in (grammar; NEUTRAL) the slot designed (grammar; NEUTRAL) for these TV devices (grammar; MINOR). (substitution; MINOR) time performed (mistranslated; MINOR) these steps (grammar; MINOR), you must go to (capitalisation; MINOR), configuration (inconsistent with terminology resource; MINOR), support (inconsistent with terminology resource; MINOR), software (capitalisation; MINOR) (omission; MINOR) (punctuation; NEUTRAL) and update (capitalisation; MINOR) now. Importantly, (grammar; MINOR) do not turn off the TV or remove this unit (inconsistent with terminology resource; MINOR). (punctuation; MINOR) USB until the upgrade (omission; MINOR) (punctuation;</p>
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			<p>MINOR Done! (mistranslation; MINOR)</p>
<p>¡Hola, hola! Hoy vamos a comentar los beneficios de tener un televisor con inteligencia artificial. ¡Comenzamos! Los nuevos procesadores de los televisores Samsung con inteligencia artificial identifican nuestros hábitos de consumo para adaptarse a lo que vemos y mejorar la calidad. No solo corrige los defectos, sino que se trata de un proceso de aprendizaje por el cual mejora imagen y sonido. ¿Cómo me beneficio yo de ello? Ahora los televisores Samsung realizan los ajustes adecuados para que veas con mayor claridad tus deportes favoritos. Por ejemplo,</p>	<p>Hello, hello! Today we are going to talk about the benefits of having a TV with artificial intelligence. Let's get started! Samsung's new television processors with artificial intelligence identify our viewing habits to adapt to what we watch and improve the quality. It not only corrects defects, but it is a learning process by which it enhances image and sound. How do I benefit from it? Samsung TVs now make the right adjustments so that you can watch your favorite sports more clearly. For example, in a tennis match, it will offer better</p>	<p>Hello (punctuation; MINOR) hello (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) today we are going to discuss (language register; NEUTRAL) the benefits of having a television (language register; MINOR) with artificial intelligence (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) we start with (grammar; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) the new processors of Samsung televisions (awkward style; MINOR) with artificial intelligence identifies (substitution; MINOR) our consumption (language register; NEUTRAL) habits to adapt to what we see (mistranslation; MINOR) and improve (grammar; NEUTRAL) quality (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) (grammar; MINOR) not only corrects defects (punctuation; NEUTRAL) but it is a learning process by which it improves (grammar; NEUTRAL) image and</p>	<p>Hello (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) Hello! Today we are going to comment (mistranslation; MINOR) the benefits of having I (substitution; MINOR) TV with intelligence artificial (grammar; MINOR). Shall we start? (substitution; NEUTRAL) The new television processors Samsung (textual conventions; MINOR) with artificial intelligence identify our habits of consumption (awkward style; MINOR) to adapt to what we see (mistranslation; MINOR) and improve (grammar; NEUTRAL) quality. It not only corrects defects, but it is a learning process. (punctuation; MINOR) by which it improves (grammar; NEUTRAL) image and sound. How do I benefit from it? Samsung TVs now make adjustments to give you a clearer view of your sports. (punctuation; MINOR) favorites (textual conventions;</p>

<p>en un partido de tenis ofrecerá mejor calidad en el movimiento de la pelota para que no te pierdas ningún detalle. Gracias al AI Upscaling, incluso teniendo menos calidad que la resolución del televisor, el televisor va a reescalar el contenido que estés viendo a 8k. Y nada de ruidos raros. El televisor se encarga de mejorar el audio de un diálogo sin distorsionar el sonido de toda la escena. AI Energy Mode, que se encarga de que el televisor optimice la iluminación según el contenido que estemos viendo. Te toca a ti elegir en qué gama de televisores vas a disfrutar de estos increíbles resultados. Lo tenemos claro. Neo QLED 8k,</p>	<p>quality in the movement of the ball so you don't miss any details. Thanks to AI Upscaling, even if the quality is lower than the TV's resolution, the TV will upscale the content you're watching to 8K. And no weird noises. The TV takes care of improving dialogue audio without distorting the sound of the whole scene. AI Energy Mode, which ensures that the TV optimises the brightness according to the content we are watching. It's up to you to choose from which line of televisions you'll enjoy these incredible results on. It's clear to us. Neo QLED 8K, because it has the most advanced processors.</p>	<p>sound (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) how do I benefit from it (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) now (grammar; NEUTRAL) Samsung televisions make the appropriate (language register; MINOR) adjustments so that you can see (mistranslation; MINOR) your favourite sports more clearly (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) for example (punctuation; NEUTRAL) in a tennis match (punctuation; MINOR) it will offer better quality in the movement of the ball so that you do not (language register; MINOR) miss any detail (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) thanks to the AI app scaling (substitution; MINOR) (punctuation; MINOR) even having less quality than the resolution of the television (language register; MINOR) (textual conventions; MINOR) (punctuation; MINOR) the television (language register; MINOR) will rescale (wrong term; MINOR) the content you are watching</p>	<p>(MINOR). For example, in I (substitution; MINOR) tennis match (punctuation; NEUTRAL) (grammar; MINOR) will offer better quality ball movement (grammar; NEUTRAL) so you don't miss any detail (grammar; MINOR) (punctuation; MINOR) Thanks to the skeling app. (substitution; MAJOR) (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) Even having lower quality than the TV resolution (textual conventions; MINOR), the VA (substitution; MINOR) TV to rescue (substitution; MINOR) the content you are watching at 8k (inconsistent with external reference; NEUTRAL) (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) and no weird noises. The TV is responsible for (mistranslation; MINOR) improving the audio of I (substitution; MINOR) dialogue (awkward style; MINOR) without distorting the sound of the whole scene (punctuation; MINOR), Hey hey! (substitution; MAJOR) Energy mode (capitalisation; MINOR), which ensures that the</p>
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<p>porque tiene los procesadores más avanzados.</p>		<p>to 8k (inconsistent with external reference; NEUTRAL) (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) and no strange noises (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) the television (language register; MINOR) is responsible for (mistranslation; MINOR) improving the audio of a dialogue (awkward style; MINOR) without distorting the sound of the entire (grammar; NEUTRAL) scene (punctuation; MINOR) Ai (inconsistent with external reference; MINOR) Energy Mode (punctuation; MINOR) which is responsible for ensuring that the television (language register; MINOR) optimizes the lighting (wrong term; MINOR) according to the content we are watching (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) it is (language register; NEUTRAL) up to you to choose in which range (textual conventions; NEUTRAL) of televisions you are going to (language register; NEUTRAL) enjoy these</p>	<p>television (language register; MINOR) optimizes the lighting (wrong term; MINOR) depending on the content we are watching. It is (language register; NEUTRAL) up to you to choose in which range (textual conventions; NEUTRAL) of televisions you will (language register; NEUTRAL) enjoy these incredible results. It is clear to us (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) neoq LED (spelling; MINOR) 8 k (inconsistent with external reference; NEUTRAL) (punctuation; MINOR) because it has the most advanced processors (punctuation; MINOR)</p>
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		<p>incredible results (grammar; MINOR)(punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) we are clear (mistranslation; MINOR) Neo (capitalisation; MINOR) cued (substitution; MAJOR) 8k (inconsistent with external reference; NEUTRAL) (punctuation; MINOR) because it has the most advanced processors (punctuation; MINOR)</p>	
<p>¿Hola? ¡Hola! En este How To te voy a enseñar cómo añadir tu televisor de Samsung a la app SmartThings para controlar los dispositivos inteligentes de tu hogar. Es compatible con un montón de marcas, además de con los asistentes virtuales de Samsung, Google y Amazon. Y para añadir tu televisor a SmartThings, puedes hacerlo a través del</p>	<p>Hello? Hello! In this How To, I'm going to show you how to add your Samsung TV to the SmartThings app to control the smart devices in your home. It's compatible with a bunch of brands, plus virtual assistants from Samsung, Google and Amazon. And to add your TV to SmartThings, you can register it automatically or manually, but remember, it must</p>	<p>Hello (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) hello(punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) in this How (capitalisation; MINOR) to I am going to teach you (awkward style; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) How to add your Samsung TV to the smarthing (substitution; MINOR) app to control the smart devices in your home. It is (language register; NEUTRAL) compatible with a lot of (language register; NEUTRAL) brands (punctuation; NEUTRAL) in addition to (language register; NEUTRAL) the virtual assistants of</p>	<p>Hello, (punctuation; MINOR)Hello! In this house tour (substitution; MINOR) (punctuation; MINOR) I'm going to show you how to add your Samsung TV to the Smart Things (substitution; MINOR) app to control your home's smart devices (grammar; NEUTRAL) It is (language register; NEUTRAL) compatible with I (substitution; MINOR) lot of (grammar; MINOR) brands, in addition to (language register; NEUTRAL) Samsung's virtual assistants, Google and Amazon (mistranslation; MINOR). And to add your TV to Smart Things</p>

<p>registro automático o manual. Pero recuerda, siempre tiene que estar conectado a internet. Para el registro automático, activa la aplicación y accede con tu Samsung account. Verás cómo detecta las Smart TV cercanas y aparecerá una ventana emergente de registro. Cuando veas que te pide Añadir el televisor, pulsa Añadir ahora, pulsa Inicio y selecciona Ubicación y habitación. Ahora, si la app de SmartThings no detecta tu televisor automáticamente, puedes registrarlo de manera manual. Enciende tu televisor e inicia la aplicación de SmartThings. Una vez dentro, selecciona TV, marca el PIN que</p>	<p>always be connected to the internet. For automatic registration, activate the app and log in with your Samsung account. You will see how it detects nearby Smart TVs and a registration pop-up window will appear. When you see that, it asks you to Add the TV, press Add now, press Home and select Location and room. Now, if the SmartThings app doesn't detect your TV automatically, you can register it manually. Turn on your TV and launch the SmartThings app. Once inside, select TV, type in the PIN that appears on the TV screen and wait for the process to complete and you're all set. See you in the next How To.</p>	<p>(awkward style; MINOR) Samsung, Google, and Amazon. And to add your smarthings (substitution; MINOR) TV (mistranslation; MINOR) (punctuation; MINOR) you can do it through automatic or manual registration (textual conventions; NEUTRAL), but remember it always has to be (grammar; NEUTRAL) connected to the internet. For automatic registration, activate the application (language register; MINOR) and log in with your Samsung account. You will see how it detects the Smart TVs nearby (substitution; NEUTRAL) and a registration pop-up window will appear. When you see that (punctuation; MINOR) it asks you to Add the TV, press Add. (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) Now press start (wrong term; MINOR) and select (capitalisation; MINOR) location and room. Now (punctuation; NEUTRAL) if the smarthings (substitution; MINOR) app does not detect your TV automatically, you can register it manually. Turn on your TV and start</p>	<p>(substitution; MINOR) (punctuation; MINOR) you can do it through registration automatic or manual (grammar; MINOR), but remember, always has to be (grammar; NEUTRAL) connected to the (capitalisation; NEUTRAL) Internet. For automatic registration, activate the application (language register; MINOR) and log in with your Samsung account. You will see how it detects nearby Smart TVs and I (substitution; MINOR) (omission; MINOR) pop-up window will appear. When you see that (punctuation; MINOR) it asks you to (capitalisation; MINOR) add the TV, click (grammar; NEUTRAL) (capitalisation; MINOR) add now, press start (wrong term; MINOR) and select capitalisation; MINOR) location and room. (capitalisation; MINOR) (grammar; NEUTRAL) if the Smart Things (substitution; MINOR) app does not (language register; NEUTRAL) detect your TV automatically, you can register it manually. Turn on your TV and start</p>
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<p>aparece en la pantalla del televisor y espera que el proceso se complete y ya estaría todo. Nos vemos en el próximo How To.</p>		<p>the smartthing (substitution; MINOR) application (language register; MINOR). Once inside, select TV, enter (grammar; NEUTRAL) the pin (substitution; MINOR) that appears on the TV screen and wait for the process to complete and that would be all (language register; MINOR). See you in the next howto (substitution; MINOR).</p>	<p>(grammar; NEUTRAL) the Smart Things (substitution; MINOR) app. I (substitution; MINOR) time inside, select t v (spelling; MINOR), marks (mistranslation; MINOR) the pin (spelling; MINOR) that appears on the TV screen and waits (grammar; MINOR) for the process to be completed (grammar; MINOR) and everything would be done (language register; MINOR). See you at (grammar; MINOR) the next house tour (substitution; MINOR)(punctuation; MINOR)</p>
<p>Cada paso que doy y cada zancada que doy está lleno siempre de un propósito y de una meta y de un sueño que quiero conseguir. En general, en mi día a día, aunque no esté compitiendo, utilizo mucho la meditación, pero luego justo antes de competir, yo necesito como concentrarme,</p>	<p>Every step and every stride I take is always filled with a purpose, a goal, and a dream that I want to achieve. In general, in my day-to-day life, even if I'm not competing, I meditate a lot, but then just before competing, I need to kind of focus, to be isolated. That's what</p>	<p>[Music] (insertion; NEUTRAL) Every step I take (awkward style; MINOR) and every stride I make (grammar; NEUTRAL) is always filled with a purpose (punctuation; MINOR) and (grammar; MINOR) a goal (punctuation; NEUTRAL) and a dream that I want to achieve (punctuation; MINOR) in (capitalisation; MINOR) general (punctuation; NEUTRAL) in my day to day (spelling; NEUTRAL)</p>	<p>Every step I take (awkward style; MINOR) and every stride I take is always full of I (substitution; MINOR) purpose (punctuation; MINOR) and I (substitution; MINOR) goal (punctuation; NEUTRAL) and I (substitution; MINOR) dream (grammar; NEUTRAL) I want to achieve. In general, in my day-to-day life, even if I'm not competing, I use meditation a lot (awkward style; MINOR), but</p>

<p>estar aislada. Es para eso va genial la aplicación de Unnoise con los Galaxy Buds que son la leche. Con enfoque, con pasión, puedes conseguir cosas que jamás habías pensado.</p>	<p>the Unnoise app is great for, with the Galaxy Buds, which are the best. With focus, with passion, you can achieve things you never thought you could.</p>	<p>(textual conventions; NEUTRAL) (punctuation; NEUTRAL) even if I'm not (omission; MINOR) I use meditation a lot (awkward style; MINOR) but then just before competing (punctuation; NEUTRAL) I need to (omission; NEUTRAL) concentrate and I would be (substitution; MINOR) isolated. For that, the Anis (substitution; MAJOR) app is great with the Galaxy bats (substitution; MAJOR) which are the best (unidiomatic style; NEUTRAL). With focus, with passion (punctuation; MINOR) you can achieve things you never thought possible (awkward style; NEUTRAL).</p>	<p>then just before painting (mistranslation; MINOR), I need to know how to concentrate (mistranslation; MINOR), (grammar; MINOR) be isolated. The Android (substitution; MAJOR) application is great for that (awkward style; NEUTRAL). (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) With the Galaxy Bats that are milk (mistranslation; MINOR). With focus, with passion (punctuation; MINOR) you can achieve things you have never thought of before (mistranslation; MINOR) (punctuation; MINOR)</p>
<p>¿A quién no le gusta ahorrarse un dinerito en IKEA? Te cuento, hemos lanzado las nuevas recompensas para IKEA Family, que son las nuevas ventajas para el club. Hasta ahora tenían</p>	<p>Who doesn't like to save a little money at IKEA? Let me tell you, we've launched new rewards for IKEA Family, which are the new benefits to the club. Until now, you had exclusive</p>	<p>[Music] (insertion; NEUTRAL) Who doesn't like to save a little money at IKEA? I'll tell you (unidiomatic style; MINOR). (punctuation; NEUTRAL) We've (capitalisation; NEUTRAL) launched the (grammar; NEUTRAL) new rewards for IKEA family (capitalisation; MINOR), which are</p>	<p>Who doesn't like to save I (substitution; MINOR) little money at IKEA (punctuation; MINOR) I tell you (unidiomatic style; MINOR). (punctuation; MINOR) we have (language register; MINOR) launched the (grammar; NEUTRAL) new rewards for IKEA family</p>

<p>ventajas exclusivas, descuentos y los famosos cafés gratuitos. Ahora puedes acumular los puntos y gastarlos en lo que tú quieras, en servicios, en restaurante, en productos. Vamos, en cualquier cosa dentro de IKEA. Por ejemplo, por 5 euro de compra te dan un punto, pero también puedes acumular puntos por muchas cosas más, como iniciar sesión en la web, crearte una wishlist, venir a una evento en tienda, entre otras cosas. Y luego tú te coges tus puntitos y te los gastas en lo que quieras. Por ejemplo, con 50 puntos desbloqueas un cupón de 5 euros para tu próximo envío a domicilio. Pues nada, que si todavía no eres socio, puedes meterte en la web,</p>	<p>advantages, discounts, and the famous free coffees. Now you can accumulate points and spend them on whatever you want, on services, at the restaurant, on products. Anything within IKEA. For example, for every 5 euro you spend, you get one point, but you can also accumulate points for many other things, like logging into the website, creating a wishlist, attending an in-store event, among other things. And then you take your points and spend them on whatever you want. For example, with 50 points, you unlock a 5 euro coupon for your next home delivery. So, if you're not a member yet, you can go to the website,</p>	<p>the new advantages for (grammar; NEUTRAL) the club. Until now (punctuation; NEUTRAL) they (grammar; MINOR) had exclusive advantages, discounts, and the famous free coffees. Now you can accumulate points and spend them on whatever you want; (punctuation; NEUTRAL) on services, in restaurants (grammar; MINOR), on products, (punctuation; NEUTRAL) on (grammar; NEUTRAL) anything within (capitalisation; MINOR) Ikea. For example, for a purchase of 5 euros you get one point, (awkward style; NEUTRAL) (punctuation; MINOR) but you can also accumulate points for many other things, such as (grammar; NEUTRAL) logging into the website, creating a wishlist, coming to an event in the store (awkward style; NEUTRAL), among other things (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; NEUTRAL) and then you take your points and spend them on whatever you want. For example, with 50 points you unlock a coupon for 5 (deletion; MINOR) for your next</p>	<p>(capitalisation; MINOR) (punctuation; MINOR) which are the new advantages for (grammar; NEUTRAL) the club (punctuation; MINOR) Until now (punctuation; NEUTRAL) they (grammar; MINOR) had exclusive advantages (punctuation; MINOR) discounts (punctuation; NEUTRAL) and the famous free coffees. Now you can accumulate the (grammar; MINOR) points and spend them on whatever you want (punctuation; MINOR) in restaurants (mistranslation; MINOR) (punctuation; MINOR) (grammar; MINOR) services (punctuation; MINOR) in (grammar; MINOR) products (punctuation; MINOR) We go on (mistranslation; MINOR) anything within (capitalisation; MINOR) Ikea (punctuation; MINOR) For example (punctuation; NEUTRAL) for €5 purchase (unidiomatic style; MINOR) you get 1 (substitution; MINOR) point (punctuation; MINOR) but you can also accumulate points for many other things (punctuation; MINOR) like</p>
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<p>crearte una cuenta rapidísimo y gratis, y acumular puntos. ¡Chao!</p>	<p>create an account super quickly and for free, and accumulate points. Bye!</p>	<p>home delivery. Well, if you're not a member yet, you can go to the website, create an account really quickly (unidiomatic style; MINOR) and for free, and accumulate points. Bye. (punctuation; NEUTRAL)</p>	<p>logging in on (grammar; NEUTRAL) the website (punctuation; MINOR) create (grammar; MINOR) I (substitution; MINOR) wishlist (punctuation; MINOR) come to I (substitution; MINOR) event in store (spelling; NEUTRAL) (unidiomatic style; NEUTRAL) among other things (punctuation; MINOR) And then you take your points and spend them on whatever you want (punctuation; MINOR) For example (punctuation; NEUTRAL) with 50 points you unlock I (substitution; MINOR) coupon of €5 (unidiomatic style; MINOR) for your next home delivery (punctuation; MINOR) Well nothing that points (mistranslation; MINOR) if you are (language register; NEUTRAL) not a member yet (punctuation; MINOR) you can get on the web (language register; NEUTRAL) (punctuation; MINOR) create I (substitution; MINOR) account very quickly and free (grammar; MINOR) (punctuation; NEUTRAL) and accumulate Chao points (mistranslation; MINOR).</p>
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<p>Cuando venís a IKEA a elegir un colchón nuevo, siempre nos preguntáis cómo tiene que ser. Pues hoy os lo cuento. Lo primero que necesitas saber es si vas a dormir solo o acompañado. Si duermes en pareja y alguno de los dos se mueve mucho porque no pega ojo, un colchón de muelles ensacados es la mejor opción, y si os gusta dormir acurrucaditos sin moveros mucho, un colchón viscoelástico os abrazará durante toda la noche. Lo segundo es elegir la firmeza del colchón. Si duermes siempre boca arriba o de lado y pesas más de 85 kg, te recomendamos</p>	<p>When you come to IKEA to choose a new mattress, you always ask us what it should be like. Well, today I'm going to tell you. The first thing you need to know is whether you'll be sleeping alone or with someone else. If you sleep as a couple and one of you moves a lot because you can't sleep, a pocket sprung mattress is the best option, and if you like to sleep cuddled up without moving much, a memory foam mattress will hug you all night long. The second thing is to choose the firmness of the mattress. If you always sleep on your back or side and weigh more than 85 kg,</p>	<p>(capitalisation; MINOR) when you come to IKEA to choose a new mattress (punctuation; MINOR) you always ask us what it should be like, (punctuation; NEUTRAL) (capitalisation; NEUTRAL) well (punctuation; NEUTRAL) today I'm going to tell you (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) the first thing you need to know is if (grammar; NEUTRAL) you're going to sleep alone or with someone (grammar; NEUTRAL). If you sleep as a couple and one of you moves a lot because you can't sleep, a pocket sprung mattress (inconsistent with terminology resource; NEUTRAL) is the best option, and if you like to sleep snuggled up without moving much, a memory foam mattress will hug you all night long. The second thing is to choose the firmness of the mattress. If you always sleep on your back or on your (awkward style; NEUTRAL) side and if you (awkward style;</p>	<p>When you come to IKEA to choose 1 (substitution; MINOR) new mattress (punctuation; MINOR) you always ask us what it should be like. Well (punctuation; MINOR) today I'll tell you about it (awkward style; MINOR). The first thing you need to know is whether you are going to sleep (grammar; NEUTRAL) alone or accompanied (unidiomatic style; MINOR). If you sleep as a couple and one of the 2 (substitution; NEUTRAL) moves a lot because it doesn't fit, watch out! (substitution; MINOR) 1 (substitution; MINOR) bagged spring mattress (inconsistent with terminology resource; MINOR) is the best option (punctuation; MINOR) and if you like to sleep snuggled (grammar; NEUTRAL) up without moving too much, 1 (substitution; MINOR) viscoelastic mattress (inconsistent with terminology resource; MINOR) will hug you all night long. The second</p>

<p>elegir un colchón extra firme, y si duermes boca abajo o de lado y pesas menos de 85 kg, la mejor opción es elegir un colchón de menor firmeza que se adapte a tu cuerpo. Y por último, elige bien el tamaño del colchón y no te olvides de escoger tu almohada perfecta para que los sueños no se terminen antes de tiempo.</p>	<p>we recommend choosing an extra firm mattress, and if you sleep on your stomach or side and weigh less than 85 kg, the best option is to choose a softer mattress that adapts to your body. Finally, choose the mattress size well and don't forget to choose your perfect pillow so that your dreams don't end too soon.</p>	<p>NEUTRAL weigh more than 85 kg, we recommend choosing an extra firm mattress. (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) If you sleep on your stomach or on your (awkward style; NEUTRAL) side and you (awkward style; NEUTRAL) weigh less than 85 kg, the best option is to choose a mattress with a lower firmness (unidiomatic style; MINOR) that adapts to your body. Finally, choose the size of the mattress (awkward style; NEUTRAL) well (punctuation; NEUTRAL) and don't forget to choose your perfect pillow so that your dreams don't end before their time. (awkward style; MINOR)</p>	<p>(grammar; NEUTRAL) is to choose the firmness of the mattress. If you always sleep Face (capitalisation; MINOR) up (grammar; NEUTRAL) or sideways (grammar; MINOR) and you (awkward style; NEUTRAL) weigh more than 85 kilos (inconsistent with external reference; NEUTRAL), we recommend you choose (grammar; NEUTRAL) I (substitution; MINOR) extra firm mattress (punctuation; MINOR) and if you sleep face down (grammar; NEUTRAL) or sideways (grammar; MINOR) and weigh less than 85 kilos (inconsistent with external reference; NEUTRAL), the best option is to choose I (substitution; MINOR) mattress with less firmness (unidiomatic style; MINOR) that adapts to your body. Finally, choose the size of the mattress well. (punctuation; MINOR) and don't forget to fix (mistranslation; MINOR) your pillow perfect (grammar; MINOR) so that dreams do not end prematurely (unidiomatic style; MINOR) (punctuation; MINOR)</p>
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<p>Si últimamente no le consultas nada a tu almohada porque está un poco old, es que no le has dado todo el cariño que merecía. Lo más importante para que una almohada dure mucho tiempo es que el relleno, además de cómodo, sea transpirable y absorba la humedad. Y como segundo consejo, antes de ponerles la funda del juego de sábanas, utiliza siempre fundas protectoras de almohadas. Puedes utilizar uno básico como este o uno térmico que, según el color de cada lado, te da más fresquito en verano o más calor en invierno. Con estos tips, tu almohada se convertirá en la relación más cómoda que hayas tenido.</p>	<p>If you haven't been getting anything out of your pillow lately because it's a little old, it's because you haven't given it all the love it deserved. The most important thing for a pillow to last a long time is that the filling, as well as being comfortable, is breathable and absorbs moisture. As a second tip, before putting on the sheet set cover, always use protective pillowcases. You can use a basic one like this one or a thermal one that, depending on the colour of each side, makes you cooler in summer or warmer in winter. With these tips, your pillow will become the most comfortable relationship you've ever had.</p>	<p>If you haven't checked (mistranslation; MINOR) your pillow lately because it's a little old, it's because you haven't given it all the love it deserved. The most important thing for a pillow to last a long time is that the filling, in addition to (awkward style; NEUTRAL) being comfortable, is breathable and absorbs moisture. As a second piece of advice (awkward style; NEUTRAL), before putting on the sheet set's cover (grammar; MINOR), always use protective pillowcases. You can use a basic one like this one or a thermal one that, depending on the color of each side, gives you cooler sleep in the summer or warmer sleep in the winter (unidiomatic style; MINOR). With these tips, your pillow will become the most comfortable relationship you've ever had.</p>	<p>If lately (grammar; NEUTRAL) you don't consult (mistranslation; MINOR) your pillow at all because it's a little bit (grammar; NEUTRAL) (deletion; MINOR), (grammar; MINOR) is that (grammar; NEUTRAL) you haven't given him (grammar; MINOR) all the love he (grammar; MINOR) deserved. The most important thing for I (substitution; MINOR) pillow to last a long time is that the stuffing (grammar; NEUTRAL), as well as (grammar; MINOR) comfortable, is (omission; MAJOR) and absorbs moisture. And as a second piece of advice (awkward style; NEUTRAL), before putting (grammar; NEUTRAL) the cover of the sheet set on them (awkward style; MINOR), always use protective pillowcases. You can use I (substitution; MINOR) basic like this or I (substitution; MINOR) thermal (grammar; MINOR), which (grammar; MINOR) (punctuation; MINOR) according to (awkward style; NEUTRAL) the color of each side (punctuation;</p>
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			<p>MINOR it gives you cooler weather in summer or warmer weather in winter (mistranslation; MINOR). With these tips (punctuation; MINOR) your pillow will become the relationship most comfortable you've ever had</p>
<p>¿Tú también te acabas un café y ya estás pensando en el siguiente? Pues vente arriba y móntate un coffee corner con mis productos favoritos. No es venirse arriba, y no es un coffee corner si no tienes un organizador chulísimo que sirva de lienzo para todo lo demás. Necesitas una cafetera, y si además es tetera, mejor. También necesitas unos botecitos aesthetic, y si te gusta el café, toma dos tazas, o tres, o cuatro. Ahora coloca una jarrita para la</p>	<p>Do you also finish a coffee and you're already thinking about the next one? Then come on up and set up a coffee corner with my favorite products. It's not upgrading and it's not a coffee corner if you don't have a really cool organiser that serves as a canvas for everything else. You need a coffee maker, and if it's also a teapot, even better. You also need some aesthetic jars, and if you like coffee, take two cups, or three, or four. Now get a</p>	<p>You too, when you finish a coffee, you're already thinking about the next one (unidiomatic style; NEUTRAL) (punctuation; MINOR) Well, (grammar; MINOR) come on up and set up a coffee corner with my favorite products. It's not coming up too high (mistranslation; MINOR), and it's not a coffee corner if you don't have a really cool organizer that serves as a canvas for everything else. You need a coffee maker, and if you also have a mat (mistranslation; MINOR), even better. You also need some aesthetic (substitution; MINOR) jars. And if you like coffee, have (undertranslation; MINOR) two cups, or three or four. Now place (grammar; MINOR) a (omission;</p>	<p>Do you also finish I (substitution; MINOR) coffee And (capitalisation; MINOR) you're already thinking about the next one? Then come upstairs (overtranslation; NEUTRAL) and have (mistranslation; MINOR) I (substitution; MINOR) Coffee (capitalisation; MINOR) corner with my favorite products. It's not coming on top (mistranslation; MINOR), and it is (language register; MINOR) not I (substitution; MINOR) Coffee (capitalisation; MINOR) corner if you don't have a great (undertranslation; MINOR) organizer to serve (grammar; NEUTRAL) as a canvas. (punctuation; MINOR) For (capitalisation; MINOR) everything</p>

<p>leche y las cucharillas y para terminar, una velita aromática. ¡Ya tienes tu coffee corner! Ahora te toca venirte más arriba aún y compartirla en tus redes sociales. ¡Bye!</p>	<p>small jug for the milk, and the teaspoons, and finally, a scented candle. And there you have your coffee corner! Now it's your turn to upgrade even more and share it on your social networks. Bye!</p>	<p>NEUTRAL) jug for the milk (punctuation; NEUTRAL) and the spoons (undertranslation; NEUTRAL), and to finish, an aromatic (substitution; MINOR) candle. (punctuation; MINOR) You (capitalisation; MINOR) already have unidiomatic style; MINOR) your coffee corner. (punctuation; NEUTRAL) Now it's your turn to come up even higher (mistranslation; MINOR) and share it on your social networks. Bye. (punctuation; NEUTRAL)</p>	<p>else (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) you need 1 (substitution; MINOR) coffee maker and if it is (language register; NEUTRAL) also a teapot, better (unidiomatic style; MINOR). You also need a few (awkward style; NEUTRAL) aesthetic bottles (mistranslation; MINOR) (punctuation; NEUTRAL) and if you like coffee, take 2 (substitution; NEUTRAL) cups (punctuation; MINOR) or 3 (substitution; NEUTRAL) (punctuation; NEUTRAL) or 4 (substitution; NEUTRAL) (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) now place (grammar; MINOR) 1 (substitution; MINOR) teaspoon (mistranslation; MINOR) for the milk and (grammar; NEUTRAL) teaspoons (punctuation; NEUTRAL) and finally, 1 (substitution; MINOR) aromatic (grammar; MINOR) candle. (omission; NEUTRAL) You have your (capitalisation; MINOR) Coffee corner! Now it's your turn to go even higher (mistranslation; MINOR) and</p>
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			<p>share it on your social networks <p>(punctuation; MINOR)(deletion; MINOR)</p> </p>
<p>¿Quieres ganar el premio a madre o padre del año haciendo que tu peque disfrute jugando en su habitación? Entonces tienes que pasar de esto a esto. Lo primero es elegir una zona que no interrumpa el paso y evita problemas. Yo he elegido esta. Ahora toca elegir una alfombra divertida para que los peques estén cómodos y calentitos. Añade zonas de asiento llenas de color, con unos cojines divertidos es suficiente. Ahora viene la fauna. Añade todos los peluches que consideres. Es bueno que los peques se vayan familiarizando con los</p>	<p>Do you want to win the mother or father of the year award by making your little one enjoy playing in their room? Then you have to go from this to this. First, choose an area that doesn't obstruct passageways and avoids problems. I've chosen this one. Now it's time to choose a fun rug so the little ones are comfortable and warm. Add colorful seating areas, a few fun cushions is enough. Now comes the wildlife. Add as many stuffed animals as you can think of. It's good for the little ones to become familiar with</p>	<p>(textual conventions; NEUTRAL) You want to win the award for mother or father of the year by making your little one enjoy playing in their room (punctuation; MINOR) Then you have to go from this to this (punctuation; MINOR) The first thing is to (awkward style; NEUTRAL) choose an area that does not (language register; NEUTRAL) interrupt the passage (unidiomatic style; MINOR) and avoid (grammar; MINOR) problems (punctuation; MINOR) I have (language register; NEUTRAL) chosen this one (punctuation; MINOR) Now it is (language register; NEUTRAL) time to choose a fun rug so (grammar; NEUTRAL) that the little ones are comfortable and warm (punctuation; MINOR) Add seating areas full of color (awkward style; NEUTRAL) (punctuation; NEUTRAL) with some</p>	<p>Do you want to win the Mother (capitalisation; NEUTRAL) or Father (capitalisation; NEUTRAL) of the Year (capitalisation; NEUTRAL) award? (punctuation; MINOR) making (textual conventions; MINOR) your little one enjoy playing in your (mistranslation; MINOR) room? Then you have to (unidiomatic style; MINOR) move on from this to this. The first thing to do is to (awkward style; NEUTRAL) choose (substitution; MINOR) I area that does not (language register; NEUTRAL) interrupt (unidiomatic style; MINOR) El Paso (substitution; MINOR) (punctuation; MINOR) and avoid (grammar; MINOR) problems. I have (language register; MINOR) chosen this one. Now it is (language register; NEUTRAL) time to choose (substitution; MINOR) I carpet fun (grammar; MINOR) to</p>

<p>diferentes animales. Y para que desarrollen su parte más creativa, un caballete para que pinten, dibujen o se expresen a su manera. Y bueno, jugar está muy bien, pero también, tienen que aprender a recoger, así que una buena cajita ligera y accesible es perfecta para que lo hagan ellos mismos. Ahora te toca a ti disfrutar del tiempo con ellos en su zona de juegos. ¡A por el premio!</p>	<p>different animals. And for them to develop their most creative side, an easel for them to paint, draw, or express themselves in their own way. And well, playing is great, but they also have to learn to clean up, so a good, light, and accessible little box is perfect for them to do it themselves. Now it's your turn to enjoy time with them in their play area. Go for the prize!</p>	<p>fun cushions is enough (grammar; MINOR) (punctuation; MINOR) Now comes the fauna (language register; MINOR) (punctuation; MINOR) Add all the stuffed animals that you consider (unidiomatic style; MINOR) (punctuation; MINOR) It is (language register; MINOR) good for the little ones to become familiar with the (grammar; MINOR) different animals (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) and for them to develop their most creative side (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) An easel for them to paint, draw (punctuation; NEUTRAL) or express themselves in their own way (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) and well playing is very good (unidiomatic; MINOR) (punctuation; MINOR) but they also have to learn to clean up (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) So a good (punctuation; MINOR) light (punctuation; NEUTRAL) and accessible box is perfect for them to do it themselves (punctuation; MINOR)</p>	<p>make the kids comfortable and warm (awkward style; NEUTRAL). Adds (grammar; MINOR) colourful seating areas, a few fun cushions is enough. Now comes the wildlife. Add as many stuffed animals as you consider (unidiomatic style; MINOR). It's good that the kids are getting familiar with the different animals (mistranslation; MINOR) (punctuation; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) and (grammar; NEUTRAL) to develop their most creative part (unidiomatic style; MINOR). I (substitution; MINOR) easel for them to paint, draw (punctuation; NEUTRAL) or express themselves in their own way. And well, playing is very good very good (unidiomatic style; MINOR), but they also have to learn to pick up (unidiomatic style; MINOR), so I (substitution; MINOR) (capitalisation; MINOR) Good (punctuation; MINOR) little box light and accessible (grammar; MINOR) is perfect for them to do it themselves. Now it's your turn</p>
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		Now it is (language register; MINOR) your turn to enjoy time with them in their play area (punctuation; MINOR) (omission; MINOR) for the prize (punctuation; MINOR)	(grammar; MINOR) enjoy time with them in their play area. Go for the award! (language register; NEUTRAL)
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